

Knowledge, Attitude, and Uptake of Human Papillomavirus Vaccination among Female Students in Ekiti State University

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Abstract

This study investigated knowledge, attitude, and uptake of human papillomavirus vaccination among female students of the faculty of Law in Ekiti State University. Three objectives and two hypotheses were formulated to guide this study. Cross-sectional research design was adopted in this study as primary data were gotten through the administration of questionnaire to selected 155 Law students from Ekiti State University using proportional stratified sampling technique. The data was collected and collated into Microsoft Excel and was analyzed using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) software version 27. A descriptive analysis is done mainly to assess the description of the data. Inferential statistics using Chi-Square analysis was conducted to determine the hypothesis. This study revealed that majority of participants were aware of HPV vaccination as they were broadly informed about HPV vaccination by healthcare providers. Majority 63.2% reported strongly agree while 29.7% agreed that HPV vaccination is essential to prevent cervical cancer and HPV related infection. Positive attitude towards HPV vaccination was also displayed by participants as majority (56.1% strongly agree, 40% agree) shows willingness to get HPV vaccination if given opportunity. Subsidized vaccination would increase uptake of HPV vaccination as opined by majority 85.2% strongly agreed while 8.4% agreed. Education campaigns about the benefits of HPV vaccination were strongly supported, with a large majority 85.2% reported strongly agree while 11% agreed. This study further revealed that there is a significant positive correlation ($p < 0.05$) between the level of knowledge about human papillomavirus vaccination and the uptake of the vaccination among female students of the faculty of Law in Ekiti State University. Also, there is a significant positive association ($p < 0.05$) between the attitude towards human papillomavirus vaccination and the uptake of the vaccination among female students of the faculty of Law in Ekiti State University. Recommendations such as educational campaigns

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to non-healthcare students and improved accessibility to HPV vaccinations service to students will foster adequate knowledge and increased level of uptake of HPV vaccination in the university populace.

Keywords: knowledge, Attitude, Uptake, HPV, Vaccination, Students,

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Introduction

Human Papillomavirus (HPV) is a prevalent sexually transmitted infection that can lead to cervical cancer, which is a significant public health concern globally. In Nigeria, cervical cancer is the second most common cancer among women, with HPV infection being a primary cause (Adegboyega et al., 2023). Vaccination against HPV has been proven to be effective in preventing HPV infection and subsequent cervical cancer (Karademir et al., 2022). Despite the availability and effectiveness of the HPV vaccine, its uptake remains low, particularly in developing countries like Nigeria. Vaccination against HPV has been proven to be an effective preventive measure in reducing the incidence of HPV infection and subsequent development of cervical cancer (Barrett et al., 2020). However, the success of HPV vaccination programs relies heavily on the knowledge, attitudes, and practices of the target population, especially among young women who are at the highest risk of acquiring HPV infections (Akpor et al., 2023).

The level of understanding and awareness towards the HPV vaccination can positively or negatively influence individuals. Lack of access to accurate and reliable information, or exposure to misinformation, can negatively impact vaccination decisions (Zheng et al., 2021). Lack of knowledge about HPV transmission, the types of HPV infections, and the seriousness of HPV related diseases can hinder vaccination acceptance (Adegboyega et al., 2023). Misconceptions about the vaccine's safety and side effects can act as barriers to vaccination, even among those aware of the vaccine's existence. The sources individuals rely on for information about HPV and the vaccine, such as healthcare providers, educational institutions, and media outlets, can shape their knowledge and in turn, their attitudes towards vaccination (Tung et al., 2022). Individuals with a better understanding of HPV and the vaccine are more likely to have positive attitudes, perceive the vaccine as beneficial, and express intentions to get vaccinated. Increased knowledge can translate into higher vaccination rates, as individuals are more motivated towards health seeking behaviors and thus receive the HPV vaccine (Si et al., 2022; Biyazin et al., 2022) Individuals who perceive themselves as susceptible to HPV infection and believe that HPV-related diseases, such as cervical cancer, are serious threats are more likely to have positive attitudes towards vaccination.

Positive social norms and endorsement of the HPV vaccine by trusted sources, such as healthcare providers, can foster more favorable attitudes and increase vaccination acceptance. For some individuals, moral or religious beliefs may influence their attitudes towards the HPV vaccine, particularly if it is perceived as related to sexual activity or promiscuity (Hittson et al., 2023). Negative attitudes stemming from these religious beliefs can pose barriers to HPV vaccination acceptance. Attitudes towards practical factors, such as cost, accessibility, and convenience of vaccination, can also impact vaccination behavior. Positive attitudes towards the availability and ease of accessing the HPV vaccine can facilitate vaccination uptake (Kitz et al., 2023).

The problem at hand is the limited knowledge, varied attitudes, and inconsistent practices regarding HPV vaccination among the target population. Despite the availability of HPV vaccine and efforts to promote vaccination programs, there may be significant gaps in awareness and understanding of HPV leading to insufficient knowledge, misconceptions, misinformation, and hesitancy towards vaccination, hindering the benefits of vaccination among this specific population. The uptake of HPV vaccination remains suboptimal in many populations, including University students. This study aims to assess the knowledge, attitude

and uptake of human papillomavirus vaccination among female students of the faculty of Law in Ekiti state University

Specifically, the objectives were to:

1. assess the level of knowledge of human papillomavirus vaccination among female students of the faculty of Law in Ekiti State University;
2. determine the attitude of female students of the faculty of Law in Ekiti State University towards human papillomavirus vaccination; and
3. assess the level of uptake of human papillomavirus vaccination among female students of the faculty of Law in Ekiti State University.

Methodology

This study used a cross-sectional design to assess the knowledge, attitude and uptake of human papillomavirus vaccination among female students of the Faculty of Law in Ekiti State University. It has six departments which are Public Law, Private and Property Law, Business and Industrial Law, Department of Jurisprudence and International Law. The total population of female students of the Faculty of Law are 215; 100 level are 45, 200 level are 38, 300 level are 43, 400 level are 34 while 500 level are 55. Sample size was calculated using Taro Yamane's sample size formula.

$n = N / (1 + N [E]^2)$, n = calculated sample size, N (total population) = 215,

E (margin of error) = 0.05

$n = 215 / (1 + 215 [0.05]^2)$

$= 215 / (1 + 0.5275)$

$= 215 / 1.5275$

$n = 140.75$, approximately 141 female students of the faculty of Law. A proportional stratified sampling technique was used to select the required sample size of 138. Attrition rate of 10 percent when added, it amounts to 155. A total of 155 female respondents were approached individually, introduced to the study in a more detailed way, and the purpose of the study was explained to them. Their consent was sought and the questionnaire was given to them to fill out.

A self-designed questionnaire with section A to E. Face and content validity of the instrument were ensured by comparing the designed questionnaire to instruments from similar, published research. The reliability of the instrument was done via pilot study in which 10% of the instrument (16) was tested using Cronbach's Alpha and a value of 0.83 was gotten. The data was collected and sorted, it was descriptively analysed using percentages, mean, median, bar charts etc. Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 27 was used to analyze the data collected. An application for Ethical clearance to carry out the study was filed at the Ekiti State University Office of Research, Development and Innovation. Upon approval, the respondents approached, consent was sought, confidentiality was maintained and no harm got to the patient.

Results

Table 1: Knowledge of Human Papillomavirus Vaccination

Variables	Responses	Frequency	Percentage
I have heard of the Human Papillomavirus (HPV)	Strongly Disagree	6	3.9%
	Disagree	9	5.8%
	Neutral	0	0.0%
	Agree	96	61.9%
	Strongly Agree	44	28.4%

Healthcare personnel have provided me information about HPV	Strongly Disagree	5	3.2%
	Disagree	3	1.9%
	Neutral	18	11.6%
	Agree	51	32.9%
	Strongly Agree	78	50.3%
Social media is a significant source of my knowledge about HPV	Strongly Disagree	0	0.0%
	Disagree	26	16.8%
	Neutral	9	5.8%
	Agree	86	55.5%
	Strongly Agree	34	21.9%
HPV infection can be transmitted through sexual contact	Strongly Disagree	0	0.0%
	Disagree	6	3.9%
	Neutral	0	0.0%
	Agree	30	19.4%
	Strongly Agree	119	76.8%
The HPV vaccine is essential for preventing cervical cancer and other HPV-related diseases	Strongly Disagree	5	3.2%
	Disagree	0	0.0%
	Neutral	6	3.9%
	Agree	46	29.7%
	Strongly Agree	98	63.2%
Females should be vaccinated against HPV as early as nine years old, before sexual exposure	Strongly Disagree	0	0.0%
	Disagree	0	0.0%
	Neutral	5	3.2%
	Agree	47	30.3%
	Strongly Agree	103	66.5%
The HPV vaccine is recommended for both males and females	Strongly Disagree	0	0.0%
	Disagree	29	18.7%
	Neutral	15	9.7%
	Agree	49	31.6%
	Strongly Agree	62	40.0%

The data presented in Table 1 provides an overview of respondents' knowledge of Human Papillomavirus (HPV) vaccination. When asked if they had heard of HPV, the majority of respondents agreed or strongly agreed, with 96 individuals (61.9%) agreeing and 44 individuals (28.4%) strongly agreeing. Only a small fraction strongly disagreed (3.9%) or disagreed (5.8%). When asked if social media was a significant source of their knowledge about HPV, 86 respondents (55.5%) agreed and 21.9% strongly agreed. A minority disagreed (26 respondents, 16.8%) or were neutral (5.8%), and none strongly disagreed. Regarding whether healthcare personnel provided information about HPV, a substantial number of respondents strongly agreed (50.3%) and agreed (32.9%). Few respondents strongly disagreed (3.2%) or disagreed (1.9%), with (11.6%) remaining neutral. Regarding whether HPV infection can be transmitted through sexual contact, a significant majority strongly agreed (119 respondents, 76.8%) and agreed (19.4%). A small number of respondents disagreed (3.9%), and none were neutral or strongly disagreed. When asked if the HPV vaccine is essential for preventing cervical cancer and other HPV-related diseases, most

respondents strongly agreed (63.2%) and agreed (29.7%). A few respondents strongly disagreed (3.2%) or were neutral (3.9%), and none disagreed. Regarding whether females should be vaccinated against HPV as early as nine years old, before sexual exposure, a significant majority strongly agreed (66.5%) and agreed (30.3%). Only 5 respondents (3.2%) were neutral, and none disagreed or strongly disagreed. Finally, when asked if the HPV vaccine is recommended for both males and females, 40.0% strongly agreed and 31.6% agreed. However, 18.7% disagreed and 9.7% were neutral, with none strongly disagreeing.

Fig: 1: Responses about Knowledge of HPV vaccination

Table 2: Responses on the Attitude towards Human Papillomavirus Vaccination

Variables	Responses	Frequency	Percentage
Only sexually active individuals are at risk of HPV infection	Strongly Disagree	31	20.0%
	Disagree	41	26.5%
	Neutral	32	20.6%
	Agree	18	11.6%
	Strongly Agree	33	21.3%
HPV vaccination should only be taken when intending to become sexually active	Strongly Disagree	31	20.0%
	Disagree	55	35.5%
	Neutral	6	3.9%
	Agree	48	31.0%
	Strongly Agree	15	9.7%
My religious beliefs do not support receiving the HPV vaccine	Strongly Disagree	6	3.9%
	Disagree	86	55.5%
	Neutral	15	9.7%
	Agree	23	14.8%
	Strongly Agree	25	16.1%
I believe that taking contraceptives prevents HPV infection	Strongly Disagree	3	1.9%
	Disagree	85	54.8%
	Neutral	17	11.0%
	Agree	35	22.6%
	Strongly Agree	15	9.7%

I feel regretful for not receiving the HPV vaccine earlier in life	Strongly Disagree	12	7.7%
	Disagree	62	40.0%
	Neutral	9	5.8%
	Agree	15	9.7%
	Strongly Agree	57	36.8%
I am willing to be vaccinated against HPV if given the opportunity	Strongly Disagree	0	0.0%
	Disagree	6	3.9%
	Neutral	0	0.0%
	Agree	62	40.0%
	Strongly Agree	87	56.1%
Educating individuals on HPV vaccination should begin in primary and secondary school	Strongly Disagree	0	0.0%
	Disagree	5	3.2%
	Neutral	6	3.9%
	Agree	11	7.1%
	Strongly Agree	133	85.8%

The data presented in Table 2 provides an overview of respondents' attitudes towards Human Papillomavirus (HPV) vaccination. When asked if only sexually active individuals are at risk of HPV infection, responses were varied. A notable portion strongly disagreed (20.0%) or disagreed (26.5%). Others were neutral (20.6%), agreed (11.6%), or strongly agreed (21.3%). Regarding whether HPV vaccination should only be taken when intending to become sexually active, most respondents disagreed (35.5%) or strongly disagreed (20.0%). However, a significant number agreed (31.0%) or strongly agreed (9.7%), with a few remaining neutral (3.9%). When asked if their religious beliefs do not support receiving the HPV vaccine, more than half disagreed (55.5%), and a smaller number strongly disagreed (3.9%). Some respondents agreed (14.8%) or strongly agreed (16.1%), while 15 respondents (9.7%) remained neutral. In terms of belief that taking contraceptives prevents HPV infection, the majority disagreed (54.8%) or strongly disagreed (1.9%). Some agreed (22.6%) or strongly agreed (9.7%), and 17 respondents (11.0%) were neutral. When asked if they feel regretful for not receiving the HPV vaccine earlier in life, responses were split, with a significant number strongly agreeing (36.8%) or disagreeing (40.0%). Others were neutral (5.8%), agreed (9.7%), or strongly disagreed (7.7%). Regarding willingness to be vaccinated against HPV if given the opportunity, a large majority strongly agreed (56.1%) or agreed (40.0%). Only a small fraction disagreed (3.9%). Finally, when asked if educating individuals on HPV vaccination should begin in primary and secondary school, an overwhelming majority strongly agreed (85.8%) or agreed (7.1%). Only a few respondents disagreed (3.2%) or were neutral (3.9%), with none strongly disagreeing.

Fig: 2: Responses on if only sexually active individuals are at risk of HPV infection

Table 3: Responses on Level of Uptake of Human Papillomavirus Vaccination

Variables	Responses	Frequency	Percentage
I am unaware of where to get the HPV vaccine	Strongly Disagree	13	8.4%
	Disagree	94	60.6%
	Neutral	10	6.5%
	Agree	33	21.3%
	Strongly Agree	5	3.2%
The cost of the HPV vaccine is a significant barrier for me	Strongly Disagree	0	0.0%
	Disagree	5	3.2%
	Neutral	19	12.3%
	Agree	45	29.0%
	Strongly Agree	86	55.5%
The HPV vaccine is not easily accessible in my community	Strongly Disagree	0	0.0%
	Disagree	38	24.5%
	Neutral	25	16.1%
	Agree	74	47.7%
	Strongly Agree	18	11.6%
Fear of pain from the needle discourages me from getting the vaccine	Strongly Disagree	5	3.2%
	Disagree	70	45.2%
	Neutral	27	17.4%
	Agree	25	16.1%
	Strongly Agree	28	18.1%
I feel embarrassed to request the HPV vaccine from healthcare workers	Strongly Disagree	3	1.9%
	Disagree	77	49.7%
	Neutral	10	6.5%
	Agree	52	33.5%
	Strongly Agree	13	8.4%
Free or subsidized vaccination would	Strongly Disagree	0	0.0%
	Disagree	10	6.5%

increase uptake	Neutral	0	0.0%
	Agree	13	8.4%
	Strongly Agree	132	85.2%
Education campaigns about the benefits of HPV vaccination would encourage more individuals to get vaccinated	Strongly Disagree	0	0.0%
	Disagree	0	0.0%
	Neutral	6	3.9%
	Agree	17	11.0%
	Strongly Agree	132	85.2%
Religious leaders advocating for HPV vaccination would improve acceptance	Strongly Disagree	5	3.2%
	Disagree	0	0.0%
	Neutral	15	9.7%
	Agree	40	25.8%
	Strongly Agree	95	61.3%
Peer influence (e.g., friends or family recommending vaccination) would motivate me to get vaccinated	Strongly Disagree	5	3.2%
	Disagree	2	1.3%
	Neutral	34	21.9%
	Agree	29	18.7%
	Strongly Agree	85	54.8%
Having a female healthcare provider available to administer the vaccine would make me feel more comfortable	Strongly Disagree	0	0.0%
	Disagree	10	6.5%
	Neutral	0	0.0%
	Agree	19	12.3%
	Strongly Agree	126	81.3%

The data in Table 3 provides insights into the level of uptake of Human Papillomavirus (HPV) vaccination. When asked if they were unaware of where to get the HPV vaccine, the majority disagreed (60.6%) or strongly disagreed (8.4%). However, a notable portion agreed (21.3%) or strongly agreed (3.2%), and some were neutral (6.5%).

Regarding the cost of the HPV vaccine as a significant barrier, more than half strongly agreed (55.5%) or agreed (29.0%), with fewer respondents being neutral (12.3%) or disagreeing (3.2%). When asked if the HPV vaccine is not easily accessible in their community, nearly half agreed (47.7%) or strongly agreed (11.6%), while a significant portion disagreed (24.5%) or were neutral (16.1%). Fear of pain from the needle was a concern, with a notable number of respondents disagreeing (45.2%) or strongly disagreeing (3.2%). However, some agreed (16.1%) or strongly agreed (18.1%), and others were neutral (17.4%). Regarding embarrassment to request the HPV vaccine from healthcare workers, nearly half disagreed (49.7%) or strongly disagreed (1.9%). However, a significant number agreed (33.5%) or strongly agreed (8.4%), with some remaining neutral (6.5%). When asked if free or subsidized vaccination would increase uptake, an overwhelming majority strongly agreed (85.2%) or agreed (8.4%), with only a few respondents disagreeing (6.5%). Education campaigns about the benefits of HPV vaccination were strongly supported, with a large

majority strongly agreeing (85.2%) or agreeing (11.0%), and a few being neutral (3.9%). Religious leaders advocating for HPV vaccination was seen as beneficial, with most respondents strongly agreeing (61.3%) or agreeing (25.8%). A small number were neutral (9.7%) or strongly disagreed (3.2%). Peer influence was also seen as a motivating factor, with the majority strongly agreeing (54.8%) or agreeing (18.7%). Some were neutral (21.9%), disagreed (1.3%), or strongly disagreed (3.2%). Finally, having a female healthcare provider available to administer the vaccine was strongly favored, with the vast majority strongly agreeing (81.3%) or agreeing (12.3%), and a few disagreeing (6.5%).

Fig: 2: Responses on awareness of where to get the HPV vaccine

Testing of Hypothesis

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant association between the level of knowledge about human papillomavirus vaccination and the uptake of the vaccination among female students of the faculty of Law in Ekiti State University.

Table 4: Chi-Square analysis to determine association between the level of knowledge about human papillomavirus vaccination and the uptake of the vaccination among Female students

Level of knowledge about human papillomavirus vaccination	Uptake of the vaccination among female students			Chi-Square (X ²) value	Df	p-value
	Inadequate Knowledge	Adequate Knowledge	Total			
Strongly Disagree	0(0.0%)	5(3.2%)	5(3.2%)	29.590	4	<0.001
Disagree	0(0.0%)	70(45.2%)	70(45.2%)			
Neutral	6(3.9%)	21(13.5%)	27(17.4%)			
Agree	0(0.0%)	25(16.1%)	25(16.1%)			
Strongly Agree	0(0.0%)	28(18.1%)	28(18.1%)			

Total	6(3.9%)	149(96.1%)	155(100%)			
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Data presented in table 4 shows that there is an association ($p < 0.05$) between the level of knowledge about human papillomavirus vaccination and the uptake of the vaccination among female students of the faculty of Law in Ekiti State University as p -value < 0.001 which is lesser than statistically significant value 0.05. The chi-square value is 29.590 at 4 degree of freedom. The result confirmed that null hypothesis was rejected.

Discussion of Findings

This study examined knowledge, attitudes, and uptake of Human Papillomavirus (HPV) vaccination among female students of the Faculty of Law at Ekiti State University and identified factors influencing vaccination behavior. Overall, the findings demonstrate relatively high awareness and positive attitudes toward HPV vaccination; however, uptake remains constrained by structural and economic barriers. Regarding knowledge of HPV and its vaccination, the majority of respondents demonstrated substantial awareness. Most participants had heard of HPV, with a combined 90.3% agreeing or strongly agreeing, a finding consistent with studies conducted by Isara et al. (2021) and Rocha et al. (2022), which reported high awareness levels and knowledge of the existence of HPV vaccines among similar populations. This suggests that information about HPV has become increasingly accessible, likely due to expanded health communication efforts and digital platforms.

Healthcare personnel were identified as an important source of information, as over three-quarters of respondents agreed that they had received HPV-related information from health workers. This aligns with evidence emphasizing the role of healthcare providers in improving vaccine knowledge and acceptance. However, social media emerged as an even more prominent source of information, with more than 80% of respondents acknowledging it as a significant contributor to their HPV knowledge. This supports findings by Khalil et al. (2023), who observed that most participants relied heavily on internet-based platforms for HPV-related information. While this broadens access, it also underscores the need for accurate and evidence-based digital health messaging to counter misinformation.

Knowledge of HPV transmission and prevention was notably high. Nearly all respondents correctly identified sexual contact as a mode of HPV transmission, and the majority strongly agreed that HPV vaccination is essential for preventing cervical cancer and other HPV-related diseases. These findings corroborate Rabiou et al. (2020), who reported strong awareness of the protective role of HPV vaccination against cervical cancer. Furthermore, respondents demonstrated good knowledge of vaccination timing, with most agreeing that females should be vaccinated as early as nine years of age before sexual debut. This aligns with recommendations and findings by Sinshaw et al. (2022), emphasizing the importance of early vaccination prior to exposure.

Awareness of HPV vaccination for both sexes was also relatively high, although less unanimous compared to other knowledge indicators. While most respondents agreed that both males and females should be vaccinated, a notable proportion expressed uncertainty or disagreement. This finding mirrors Rocha et al. (2022), who reported varying levels of awareness regarding HPV vaccination across genders, suggesting the need for broader public education emphasizing the benefits of vaccinating both males and females.

In terms of attitudes toward HPV vaccination, respondents demonstrated generally positive perceptions, though some misconceptions persisted. Opinions were divided on whether only sexually active individuals are at risk of HPV infection, indicating partial misunderstanding of

HPV susceptibility. Similarly, views were mixed on whether vaccination should only be taken when intending to become sexually active. Despite this, a higher proportion disagreed with delayed vaccination, consistent with Agadayi et al. (2022), who reported that most respondents supported vaccination before sexual debut.

Religious beliefs did not appear to pose a major barrier, as more than half of respondents disagreed that their faith opposed HPV vaccination. This suggests that cultural or religious resistance may be less influential among this population than previously reported in some contexts. Additionally, most respondents correctly rejected the misconception that contraceptive use prevents HPV infection, reflecting improved sexual health knowledge. Emotional responses toward vaccination history were mixed, with some respondents expressing regret for not being vaccinated earlier, while others did not. Importantly, willingness to receive the HPV vaccine if given the opportunity was overwhelmingly high, with nearly all respondents expressing agreement. This aligns with Rocha et al. (2022), who found strong willingness among both men and women to receive the HPV vaccine when accessible. Furthermore, there was strong consensus that HPV education should begin in primary and secondary schools, reinforcing findings by Khalil et al. (2023), which demonstrated that early sexual education significantly improves HPV knowledge and vaccine uptake.

Despite favorable knowledge and attitudes, HPV vaccine uptake was hindered by several barriers. While most respondents knew where to access the vaccine, cost emerged as a major obstacle. A large majority identified vaccine cost as a significant barrier, consistent with findings by Agadayi et al. (2022) and Akpor et al. (2023), who reported that high cost and lack of insurance coverage significantly reduced vaccination rates. Accessibility issues were also noted, with many respondents indicating that the vaccine was not easily available within their communities.

Psychosocial barriers such as fear of injection pain and embarrassment when requesting the vaccine from healthcare workers were present but less dominant. Nevertheless, a substantial proportion supported interventions aimed at improving uptake. Free or subsidized vaccination was strongly endorsed, corroborating Olofin-Samuel et al. (2024), who identified cost reduction as a key strategy for improving vaccination coverage. Educational campaigns, peer influence, involvement of religious leaders, and availability of female healthcare providers were also widely supported, highlighting the importance of culturally sensitive and community-based approaches.

Finally, this study established a statistically significant association ($p < 0.05$) between knowledge of HPV vaccination and vaccine uptake among respondents. This finding reinforces the critical role of health education in improving vaccination behavior and underscores the need for sustained awareness campaigns to translate knowledge into practice.

Conclusion

This study concludes that the majority of participants were aware of Human Papillomavirus (HPV) vaccination, with healthcare providers playing a key role in disseminating information about HPV and its prevention. Participants generally recognized the importance of HPV vaccination in preventing cervical cancer and other HPV-related infections. Overall, a positive attitude toward HPV vaccination was observed, as many participants expressed willingness to receive the vaccine if given the opportunity.

The findings further indicate that financial considerations significantly influence vaccine uptake, with participants suggesting that subsidized or free vaccination would improve acceptance and utilization. There was also strong support for educational campaigns aimed at increasing awareness of the benefits of HPV vaccination, highlighting the importance of sustained health education initiatives within the university setting.

Importantly, the study established a significant positive relationship between knowledge of HPV vaccination and its uptake among female students of the Faculty of Law at Ekiti State University. Similarly, a significant positive association was observed between attitudes toward HPV vaccination and vaccination uptake. These findings underscore the critical role of adequate knowledge and favorable attitudes in promoting preventive health behaviors.

Recommendations

1. Nurses and public health professionals should collaborate with academic institutions to systematically integrate comprehensive HPV education into student-focused programs, curricula, and extracurricular health promotion activities. Such integration will enhance students' awareness and understanding of HPV infection and the preventive benefits of vaccination.
2. Nurses, in collaboration with policymakers and university authorities, should advocate for the establishment of on-campus HPV vaccination clinics and the implementation of subsidized vaccination schemes. These measures would help reduce financial, structural, and accessibility barriers that limit vaccine uptake among students.
3. Continuous professional development initiatives for nurses are essential to strengthen their capacity to engage effectively with diverse populations. Ongoing training will equip nurses with up-to-date knowledge and culturally sensitive communication skills necessary for promoting HPV vaccination and other preventive healthcare interventions across varied sociocultural and educational contexts.

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